
ASSESSMENT OF COSTS AND RETURNS OF SOME DOMESTIC SOLID WASTES OFF-TAKE IN EBONYI STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed costs and returns of some domestic solid wastes off-take in 2023 and 2024 in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select 60 respondents for the study. Primary data were collected with the aid of structured questionnaire administered in the form of interview schedule. Data were generated and analysed using descriptive statistics, and gross margin analysis. Majority (66.7%) of respondents were males and 33.3% were females. Their age ranged from 31 to 40 years for majority and 5% of 51 to 60 years for very few. Majority (58.3%) of the respondents were married with 55% of the respondents having household size between 1 - 5 persons. Similarly, 51.7% of respondents had secondary education and unemployed. Additionally, majority (48.3%) of the respondents had 0 - 5 years experience in the business. The results also revealed that majority (53.3%) of the respondents in the study area had monthly income or returns between ₦400,001 and ₦600,000 generated in the business. Based on the findings of this study, there is need for youths engagement as there is profitability of solid waste off-take as a means of recycling to reduce unemployment in the area. Governments should implement tax incentives and subsidies to encourage the businesses and individuals to adopt off-takes as means of wastes reduction and minimization practices, which would keep the environment clean and reduce wastes disposal costs.

Keyword: Costs, Returns, Domestic solid wastes, Off-take, Ebonyi State

1. INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanization, coupled with insufficient government facilities, have led to a situation where wastes collection services are seldomly provided in an equitable, and consistent way. Domestic solid wastes refer to solid materials that are generated and disposed off from household activities (Hans and Maria, 2019). Wastes management or wastes disposal includes the processes and actions required to manage wastes from its generation to its final disposal (Cristina and Maria, 2019). This includes the collection, transportation treatment and disposal of wastes, as well as monitoring and regulation of the wastes, such as wastes-related laws, technologies, economics and mechanisms (IFC, 2014).

Solid wastes dumps apart from their gory sight that destroy the aesthetic beauty of the environment have always affected the people's health by decomposing to produce provoking odour or contaminating our drinking water. This no doubt, causes avoidable epidemics. It should be recalled that, prior to the creation of Ebonyi State in 1996, Abakaliki urban was faced with myriad of environmental problems ranging from inadequate environmental education and awareness campaign to poor personal and environmental hygiene. Every street was adorned with heaps of refuse while Iyiokwu and Iyiudele rivers, in Abakaliki urban were converted to dumping arena for domestic wastes and human excreta. Proper management of wastes is important for building sustainable and livable cities, but it remains a challenge for many developing countries and cities.

In Abakaliki the capital city and entire geopolitical zones of Ebonyi State, indiscriminate disposal of solid domestic wastes along the roads, streets, street drains, residential halls, and public places are no longer common. This is because wastes off-takers move from house to house, shops and public and private offices to buy solid wastes for reuse and recycling. It has, therefore, created job opportunity, employment opportunity, reduced poverty and enhances the livelihood of the people at the location. Report of Heinemann *et al.* (2003) found that effective wastes management is relatively expensive, usually comprising 20%–50% of municipal budgets.

Wastes off-take, among many others, transform domestic and industrial wastes into wealth (Oyeniyi, 2011). Their activities that reduce wastes from dumpsite to only organic wastes, directly or indirectly help agencies responsible for wastes management by reducing their costs. Domestic solid wastes off-takes are very visible; in many wastes dumpsites which represent the most notable elements in the informal recycling scene which hinges around the following five major activities namely: wastes separation, collection, transportation, processing of recyclables, and finally trading of the processed materials (Nzeadibe and Iwuoha, 2008). The recycling process begins with wastes picking, an activity in which a large number of people find great employment opportunity in both developing and under developing economies such as Nigeria compared to USA.

The growing population in Nigeria alone is expected to trigger concerns in areas of population flows, urban infrastructure and service delivery, food security, resource and wealth distribution, insecurity/conflicts, and environmental degradation; all of which have the capacity to impact the urban system. Ebonyi State - Nigeria's economic hub, with a population of more than 4 million generates an estimated 5,000 metric tonnes of domestic solid wastes daily, which comes to about 1.2 million tonnes of domestic solid wastes annually (Onwe, Uduma, and Nwachukwu, 2015). In the past few years, attention of research on solid wastes management in Ebonyi State and Nigeria in particular has focused essentially on contextualizing wastes recycling as an approach to urban environmental management and livelihoods (Akhtar and Sarmah, 2020). This has created a gap in knowledge on the costs and

returns of domestic solid wastes off-takes in the study area as little or no research attention has been directed to this aspect of wastes. To address this gap, the study described the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents and determined costs returns of domestic solid wastes off-take in the study areas.

2. METHODOLOGY

Site Description

This research was carried out in Ebonyi North, Ebonyi Central and Ebonyi South of Ebonyi State. Ebonyi North is geographically located on Longitude N06°12.4950 and latitude 008°06.813E, Ebonyi Central on longitude 06°09.3844 and Latitude 008°08.0792 and Ebonyi South on longitude N06°05.8911 and 008°07.9307 respectively. Ebonyi state has an altitude above the sea level of about 245 m (Onwe *et al.*, 2015). The population of this study consisted of all residence in three zones of Ebonyi State. From the last census of 2006, information showed that Ezza South recorded 133,625, Onicha recorded 236,609 and Ishielu recorded 152,581 (NPC, 2006). Ebonyi state is characterized as a tropical climate with seasonal conditions due to influence of North – South fluctuation of a discontinuity zone between the dry continental air and the humid maritime air. The annual temperature varies from 27°C for dry season to 31 °C for wet seasons. The relative humidity of the area ranges from 60 to 80% for dry and rainy season. Dominant cultivable arable cereals are (rice, maize), vegetables and fruits. The residents are mainly farmers, government workers, business persons, traders, workers of private sectors and artisans.

Sampling Methods

A stratified random sampling technique was adopted and the study area was divided into three (3) zones represented by the wastes off-take sites. The zones were narrowed down to off-take sites: (i) Ebonyi North – Abakaliki – Ogbе-Hausa; (ii) Ebonyi Central – Ezza-south – Onueke; (iii) Ebonyi south – Onicha – Abaomege. Twenty (20) respondents were randomly selected from each of the three zones giving a total of 60 respondents selected for the study. The questionnaires were distributed to the selected respondents.

Field data

Field data were generated every month for two years (2023 and 2024). Domestic solid wastes generated each month were weighed with weighing balance, costs and returns (profit) generated after sales from each month for the period of 2 years were also recorded. At the end, data were collated, computed and subjected to statistical analysis.

Questionnaire design/Administration

Questionnaires were designed based on the research objectives. The questionnaires were categorized into two sections. Section one sought information about the socio-economic characteristics of respondents. Section two of the questionnaire sought information on costs and returns on domestic solid wastes buying and selling in the study area. The ideas and opinions of the respondents on the ways to improve the wastes profitability and general quality of the study area were noted. A total of 60 questionnaires were administered to the respondents selected for the study.

Gross Margin Model

Gross margin (GM) = TR – TVC where, TR = Total Revenue, TV = Total Variable cost;
Profit = TR – TC; where, TR = Total Revenue; TC = Total cost

Statistical Analysis

The data collected from this study were analyzed using descriptive method of data analysis such as frequency, percentage, mean, and gross margin analysis. Objective i was achieved using frequency, percentage, mean. Objective ii was analysed using gross margin analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents

The socio-economic attributes analysed include: sex, age, marital status, level of education, major occupation, alternative livelihoods, experience and monthly income. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 1. Majority (66.7%) of respondents were males, 33.3% were females. This implies that males dominated in solid wastes off-take business. This is so because wastes off-taking is labour intensive and only very few females are involved. This is corroborating the findings of Olagunju *et al.* (2020), who reported that 84% – 90% of the household heads in Nigeria were male.

The range of majority (38.3%) was between 31 to 40 years, while very few (5%) were aged between 51 to 60 years. This implies that the respondents were in their youthful, active and productive age. Age is important indicator that determines the kind of people this type of profession because, the work is for youths and not the elderly who may not withstand the stress of wastes off-taking which involves movement from one wastes dump site to another in searching for wastes products of interest. This result is not in line with the work of Egun (2012) who reported that age range of solid wastes enterprise owners was between 20 - 30 years. Again, majority (58.3%) were married; while very few (5%) of the respondents were widowed. This implies that solid wasted off-takers are dominated by married men who understand what responsibility entails being married and look out ways for generating income to cater for the family. This indicates that there is a stable marriage condition in the area. This agrees with the findings of Henri-Ukoha *et al.*, (2015), which revealed that married people are mostly involved in livelihood activities in order to cater for the family.

Result of household size showed that majority (55%) had household size of between 1 - 5 persons, while very few (1.7%) had household size of 16 to 20 persons. This simply showed that the size of households in the study area is relatively moderate. A household with 1 – 5 members is assumed as an indicator of labor availability in the family. This study agreed with Chukwuemeka, Igwegbe and Ugwu (2012) who reported household size of 5 members and below in their study. Similarly, majority (51.7%) completed secondary education, while very few (3.3%) had no formal education. This implies that the respondents are highly knowledgeable and could read and write. In the light of high rate of unemployment in Nigeria, most may not be able to find a job in the formal sector and therefore resort to this type of profession. Though, one's level of education determines the ability of such person to make profitable decisions on investment and adopt an approach to risk management that best reduces the incidences of business failure. This indicated that formal education appears to play a significant role in determining peoples' level of risk and their ability to adapt and make appropriate decisions. This finding disagrees with the study of Ikechukwu (2015) who reported that 59.8% have no formal education, while 27.6% have only primary education, 12.1% have secondary education and no person had tertiary education. From this findings, it is obvious that majority of off-takers are not educated.

The result of the primary occupations of the respondents revealed that majority (26.7%) were unemployed, while very few (13.3%) were students and apprentices. Furthermore, 40% of the respondents were unskilled labourers, while very few (4%) were masons and welders. This implies that the respondents take the business of solid wastes as the fastest means of

generating income especially for the unemployed youths. These findings imply that the solid wastes off-takers took the business as secondary means of livelihood activities. This is because secondary livelihood activities pave ways for multiple streams of income that could increase the standards of living of the solid wastes off-takers. The result equally showed that majority (48.3%) had experience ranging from 0-5 years, while very few (3.3%) had experience of 21 years and above. With respect to the number of years in solid wastes business, it suggests that the respondents were experienced in the business venture. The result signifies that the business of solid wastes is not new in this part of the world and it is self-sustaining. Experience facilitates the identification and implementation of appropriate decisions in business to ensure the profitability of such business.

Finally, the results also revealed that majority (53.3%) had annual income level of ₦400,001 - ₦600,000, while very few (5%) of the respondents earned monthly income level below ₦200,000. The income of the respondents is low, hence the need of the business venture. This income is low considering the Nigerian economy today is indicative of the fact that the majority of the respondents live below the poverty line. This shows that income of the respondents may have negative implication on their business which would in turn affect their decision making capabilities.

Table 1: Socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents in the study area

Parameters	Frequency (N = 60)	Percentage (%)	Mean (\bar{x})
Sex			
Male	40	66.7	
Female	20	33.3	
Age (Years)			
10 – 20	4	6.7	
21 – 30	20	33.3	
31 – 40	23	38.3	33
41 – 50	10	16.7	
51 – 60	3	5.0	
Marital Status			
Single	22	36.7	
Married	35	58.3	
Widowed	3	5.0	
Household size			
1 - 5	33	55.0	
6 - 10	17	28.3	5
11 - 15	9	15.0	
16 - 20	1	1.7	
Level of education			
Primary school completed	8	13.3	
Secondary school completed	31	51.7	
Vocational/technical schooled completed	6	10.0	
Tertiary education completed	13	21.7	
No formal education	2	3.3	
Major occupation			
Farming/hunting	15	25.0	
Technician/artisan	11	18.3	
Trading	10	16.7	
Student/apprentice	8	13.3	
Unemployed	16	26.7	

Alternative livelihoods			
Mason	4	6.7	
Welder	4	6.7	
Technician/artisan	12	12.0	
Transportation	16	26.6	
Unskilled labour	24	40.0	
Experience (years)			
0 – 5	29	48.3	
6 – 10	22	36.7	6
11 – 20	7	11.7	
21 and above	2	3.3	
Annual Income (Naira)			
Below 500,000	3	5.0	
200,001 - 400,000	32	53.3	
400,001 – 600,001	13	21.7	759,430.34
Above 600,000	12	20.0	

Source: Field Survey, (2023)

Costs and returns in Domestic solid wastes off-take enterprises in the study areas

Cost and return of solid wastes off-taking (evacuation) in the study areas were analyzed using gross margin analysis. In 2023, bottles and aluminum enterprises had higher CRR, 1.73 and 1.59 respectively. The same aluminum and bottles had higher CRR in 2024. In the 2023, the average gross margin, profit and cost return ratio of the enterprises were 655,429.18, ₦550,269.18 and 1.528 respectively. In 2024, the average gross margin, profit and cost return ratio of the enterprises were 1,165,301 ₦988,581 and 1.634 respectively. The result has shown that the enterprises have performed better in 2024 than 2023. Generally, the result also highlighted the enterprises that performed better in both years which include; aluminum (1.765), bottles (1.67) and iron/metal materials (1.58). Based on the values of cost-return-ratio, it implies that the business of buying and selling of solid wastes is economically viable and profitable. Therefore, an investor could be advised to venture into the business of buying and selling domestic solid wastes. However, Scheinberg *et al.* (2010) reported that a cost-return-ratio >1 indicates that the business is profitable, and the higher the ratio, the more profitable the business.

Average Annual Costs and Returns in Domestic Plastic Wastes off-take in the study areas

The result of average annual costs and returns in domestic plastic wastes off-take in the study area were presented in Table 2. Result revealed that the total revenue was ₦390,841.9, the total cost was ₦311,600. Furthermore, the results revealed that the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦225,500, ₦86,100, ₦165,341.9, ₦79,241.9 and ₦1.25 respectively. Result also showed that in the year 2024, the total revenue was ₦621,400, the total cost was ₦421,500. Furthermore, the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦339,000, ₦82,500, ₦282,400, ₦199,900 and ₦1.47 respectively.

Table 2: Average Annual Costs and Returns in domestic plastic wastes enterprise in the study areas

Items	2023			2024		
	Qty (kg)	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)	Qty (kg)	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)
Revenue (TR)						
Plastic (water and juice bottles)	1,310.04	120	157,204.8	1,550	170	263,500
Plastic chairs	1,830	100	183,000	1,630	150	244,500
Plastic (gallons, etc)	506.362	100	50,636.2	756	150	113,400
Total Revenue (TR)			390,841.9			621,400
Variable Cost (VC)						
Plastic wastes	Lump-sum		120,000	Lump-sum		180,000
Transportation	Lump-sum		30,000	Lump-sum		45,000
Labour (Man days)	15	2000	30,000	15	3,000	45,000
Cost of Security	1	15,000	15,000	1	15,000	15,000
Tax	-	8,000	8,000	-	14,000	14,000
Loading and off-loading	Lump-sum		22,500	Lump-sum		40,000
Total Variable Cost (TVC)			225,500			339,000
Fixed Cost (FC)						
Depreciated at 10% using straight line method						
Wheel Barrow	2	20,500	61,500	4	10,500	42,000
Weighing Balance	3	5,000	15,000	3	7,500	22,500
Cost of Space (Rent) monthly cost	12	800	9,600	12	1,500	18,000
Total fixed cost (TFC)			86,100			82,500
Total Costs (TC) =TFC+TVC			311,600			421,500
Gross Margin = TR-TVC			165,341.9			282,400
Profitability (TR-TC)			79,241.9			199,900
Cost-Return-Ratio (TR/TC)			1.25			1.47

Source: Field Survey, (2023)

Average Annual Costs and Returns in domestic aluminum wastes off-take in the study areas

The result of average annual costs and returns in domestic aluminum wastes off-take in the study area were presented in Table 3. Result revealed that the total revenue was ₦3,722,874, the total cost was ₦2,339,500. Furthermore, the result revealed that the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦2,143,000, ₦196,500, ₦1,579,874, ₦1,383,374 and ₦1.59 respectively. In 2024, the total revenue was ₦4,537,500, the total cost was ₦2,332,500. Furthermore, the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross

margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦2,112,000, ₦220,500, ₦2,425,500, ₦2,205,000 and ₦1.94 respectively.

Table 3: Average Annual Costs and Returns in domestic aluminum wastes enterprise in the study areas

Items	2023			2024		
	Qty (kg)	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)	Qty (kg)	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)
Revenue (TR)						
Cans	1830	100	183,000	2400	250	600,000
Roofing sheets	5,445.96	650	3,539,874	5250	750	3,937,500
Total Revenue (TR)			3,722,874			4,537,500
Variable Cost (VC)						
Aluminum wastes	Lump-sum		1,120,000	Lump-sum		1,120,000
Transportation	Lump-sum		100,000	Lump-sum		100,000
Labour (Man days)	9	3,000	324,000	9	3,500	378,000
Cost of Security	1	360,000	360,000	1	300,000	300,000
Tax	-	14,000	14,000	-	14,000	14,000
Loading and off-loading	Lump-sum		225,000	Lump-sum		200,000
Total Variable Cost (TVC)			2,143,000			2,112,000
Fixed Cost (FC)						
Depreciated at 10% using straight line method						
Wheel Barrow	3	20,500	61,500	3	20,500	61,500
Weighing Balance	3	5,000	15,000	3	5,000	15,000
Cost of Space (Rent) annual cost	12	10,000	120,000	12	12,000	144,000
Total fixed cost (TFC)			196,500			220,500
Total Costs (TC) =TFC+TVC			2,339,500			2,332,500
Gross Margin = TR-TVC			1,579,874			2,425,500
Profitability (TR-TC)			1,383,374			2,205,000
Cost-Return-Ratio (TR/TC)			1.59			1.94

Source: Field Survey, (2023)

Average Annual Costs and Returns in domestic iron/metal material wastes off-take in the study areas

The result of average annual costs and returns in domestic iron/metal material wastes off-take in the study area were presented in Table 4. Result revealed that the total revenue was ₦1,708,506, the total cost was ₦1,093,500. Result also revealed that the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦921,000, ₦172,500, ₦787,506, ₦615,006 and ₦1.56 respectively. In 2024, result showed that the total revenue was ₦3,958,503, the total cost was ₦2,480,500. Furthermore, the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦2,284,000, ₦196,500, ₦1,674,503, ₦1,478,003 and ₦1.60 respectively.

Table 4: Average Annual Costs and Returns in domestic Iron/metal material wastes enterprise in the study areas

Items	2023			2024		
	Qty (kg)	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)	Qty (kg)	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)
Revenue (TR)						
Iron/metal materials	1,390.04	150	1,708,506	8,796.67	450	3,958,503
Total Revenue (TR)			1,708,506			3,958,503
Variable Cost (VC)						
Iron/metal material wastes	Lump-sum		372,000	Lump-sum		1,550,000
Transportation	Lump-sum		50,000	Lump-sum		75,000
Labour (Man days)	11	2500	330,000	12	2,500	330,000
Cost of Security	1	120,000	120,000	12 Months	15,000	180,000
Tax	-	14,000	14,000	-	14,000	14,000
Loading and off-loading	Lump-sum		35,000	Lump-sum		135,000
Total Variable Cost (TVC)			921,000			2,284,000
Fixed Cost (FC)						
Depreciated at 10% using straight line method						
Wheel Barrow	2	20,500	61,500	3	20,500	61,500
Weighing Balance	3	5,000	15,000	3	5,000	15,000
Cost of Space (Rent) annual cost	1	96000	96,000	12 months	10,000	120,000
Total Fixed Cost (TFC)			172,500			196,500
Total Costs (TC) =TFC+TVC			1,093,500			2,480,500
Gross Margin = TR-TVC			787,506			1,674,503
Profitability (TR-TC)			615,006			1,478,003
Cost-Return-Ratio (TR/TC)			1.56			1.60

Source: Field Survey, (2023)

Average Annual Costs and Returns in domestic Bottle wastes off-take enterprise in the study areas

The result of average annual costs and returns in domestic bottle wastes off-take enterprise in the study area were presented in Table 5. Result revealed that the total revenue was ₦1,435,800, the total cost was ₦829,000. Furthermore, the result revealed that the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦783,400, ₦45,600, ₦652,400, ₦606,800 and ₦1.73 respectively. In 2024, result showed the total revenue was ₦2,040,000, the total cost was ₦1,267,500. Furthermore, the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦1,051,500, ₦216,000, ₦988,500, ₦772,500 and ₦1.61 respectively.

Table 5: Average Annual Costs and Returns in domestic bottle wastes enterprise in the study areas

Items	2023			2024		
	Qty (kg)	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)	Qty	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)
Revenue (TR)						
Bottles	14358	100	1,435,800	20,400 bottles	100	2,040,000
Total Revenue (TR)			1,435,800			2,040,000
Variable Cost (VC)						
Bottle wastes		Lump-sum	517,900		Lump-sum	780,000
Transportation		Lump-sum	70,000		Lump-sum	70,000
Labour (Man days)	15	3000	45,000	8	3000	24,000
Cost of Security	1	120,000	120,000	1	120,000	120,000
Tax	-	14,000	14,000	-	14,000	14,000
Loading and off-loading		Lump-sum	22,500		Lump-sum	43,500
Total Variable Cost (TVC)			783,400			1,051,500
Fixed Cost (FC)						
Depreciated at 10% using straight line method						
Wheel Barrow	2	10,500	21,000	2	10,500	21,000
Weighing Balance	3	5,000	15,000	3	5,000	15,000
Cost of Space (Rent) monthly cost	12	15,000	180,000	12	15,000	180,000
Total fixed cost (TFC)			45,600			216,000
Total Costs (TC) =TFC+TVC			829,000			1,267,500
Gross Margin = TR-TVC			652,400			988,500
Profitability (TR-TC)			606,800			772,500
Cost-Return-Ratio (TR/TC)			1.73			1.61

Source: Field Survey, (2023)

Average Annual Costs and Returns in domestic Paper/book wastes off-take Enterprise in the study areas

The result of average annual costs and returns in domestic paper/book wastes off-take in the study area were presented in Table 6. Result revealed that the total revenue was ₦197,024, the total cost was ₦130,100. Furthermore, the results revealed that the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦105,000, ₦25,100, ₦92,024, ₦66,924 and ₦1.51 respectively. In 2024, result showed that the total revenue was ₦622,500, the total cost was ₦402,000.00. The result revealed that the total variable cost, total fixed cost, gross margin, profit and cost-return-ratio were ₦306,000, ₦111,500, ₦316,500, ₦205,000 and ₦1.55 respectively. The findings suggest that the domestic paper/book waste off-take business in the study area is profitable, with a cost-return-ratio of ₦1.51 in the initial year and ₦1.55 in 2024. This indicates that for every ₦1 invested, the business generates a return of ₦1.51 and ₦1.55 respectively. A Study by Chung and Poon (2001) reported that the

global waste management market is projected to grow significantly, driven by increasing waste generation and government regulations.

Table 6: Average Annual Costs and Returns in domestic paper/book wastes enterprise in the study areas

Items	2023			2024		
	Qty (kg)	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)	Qty (kg)	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost/Revenue (₦)
Revenue (TR)						
Papers	842.2	120	101,064	1850	150	277,500
Books	653	100	65,300	1450	150	217,500
Cartons, etc	306.6	100	30,660	850	150	127,500
Total Revenue (TR)			197,024			622,500
Variable Cost (VC)						
Papers	Lump-sum		50,000	Lump-sum		150,000
Transportation	Lump-sum		10,000	Lump-sum		25,000
Labour (Man days)	4	3000	12,000	2	3,000	72,000
Cost of Security	1	15,000	15,000	1	15,000	15,000
Tax	-	8,000	8,000	-	14,000	14,000
Loading and off-loading	Lump-sum		10,000	Lump-sum		30,000
Total Variable Cost (TVC)			105,000			306,000
Fixed Cost (FC)						
Depreciated at 10% using straight line method						
Wheel Barrow	1	10,500	10,500	1	10,500	10,500
Weighing Balance	1	5,000	5,000	1	5,000	5,000
Cost of Space (Rent) monthly cost	12	800	9,600	12	8,000	96,000
Total fixed cost (TFC)			25,100			111,500
Total Costs (TC) =TFC+TVC			130,100			402,000
Gross Margin = TR-TVC			92,024			316,500
Profitability (TR-TC)			66,924			205,000
Cost-Return-Ratio (TR/TC)			1.51			1.55

Source: Field Survey, (2023)

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, it concluded that the business of domestic solid wastes off-take is economically viable and profitable. Therefore, unemployed youths in Ebonyi State can be empowered economically through the profitable venture to minimize social vices caused by unemployment. There is need for youths' engagement on the profitability of solid wastes management especially on the area of waste recycling as a means of employment. Wastes management companies should provide education and training programs to their employees, ensuring they have the necessary skills to manage wastes effectively and safely.

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